

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

WHEAT GROWTH IN THE VEGETATIVE PHASE UNDER THE REGULATORY EFFECT OF FUROPYRIMIDINE DERIVATIVES

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Abstract

A comparative study of the regulatory effect of synthetic compounds, derivatives of sodium and potassium salts of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine (Methyur, Kamethur) and furopyrimidine, as well as the plant hormone auxin IAA (1*H*-indol-3-yl)acetic acid, used at a concentration of 10^{-7} M, on the growth and photosynthesis of winter wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) variety Tyra was carried out. It has been shown that furopyrimidine derivatives increased the morphometric parameters (average length of roots (mm) and average length of shoots (mm)), and biochemical parameters (content of photosynthetic pigments chlorophylls a, b, a+b and carotenoids ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)) of wheat plants during the vegetative stage. Their regulatory effect was similar to the regulatory effect plant hormone auxin IAA and synthetic compounds Methyur and Kamethur. The dependence of the chemical structure of furopyrimidine derivatives on their regulatory effect was analyzed. The practical use of most of the active synthetic compounds, Methyur, Kamethur and furopyrimidine derivatives as new regulators of growth and photosynthesis of winter wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) variety Tyra is proposed.

Keywords: wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.), IAA, Methyur, Kamethur, furopyrimidine derivatives.

Introduction. Growing one of the main cereal crops - wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) under environmental stress conditions such as increased ozone levels, soil salinization and heavy metal pollution, drought, waterlogging, temperature fluctuations that negative affect wheat growth at vegetative and reproductive stages, is an urgent problem in modern agriculture [1 - 8].

As is known, phytohormones auxins and cytokinins play a key role in the growth and adaptation of wheat and other crops to abiotic stress factors [9 - 12]. An important aspect of increasing the yield of wheat is delaying the leaf senescence in conditions of water deficit; plant hormones cytokinins are known to delay leaf senescence, activating photosynthetic processes and preventing the breakdown of photosynthetic pigments such as chlorophylls and carotenoids [13 - 16]. The use of plant hormones auxins and cytokinins [9 - 12], as well as natural biostimulants containing plant hormones [17, 18], is a promising issue for growing wheat under the influence of abiotic and biotic stress factors.

Currently, the creation of new effective and environmentally friendly wheat growth regulators is a priority task for the successful development of modern agriculture in economically developed countries [19, 20]. The newest strategy is the development of new effective wheat growth regulators based on synthetic low-molecular weight heterocyclic compounds, pyrimidine

derivatives, which exhibit physiological effects similar to plant hormones auxins and cytokinins [21 - 25].

Studies carried out on wheat and other agricultural crops have shown that pyrimidine derivatives improve seed germination and the formation and growth of plant shoots and roots, enhance photosynthetic processes in plant leaves, increase plant productivity and their adaptation to abiotic stresses [21 - 32]. Synthetic compounds, pyrimidine derivatives can be used separately or in combination with mineral fertilizers for pre-sowing seed-soaking treatment of wheat [21 - 25] and other crops [26 - 32] in low, non-toxic for the environment and human and animal health concentrations of 10^{-5} M, 10^{-6} M, 10^{-7} M [21 - 32]. Using synthetic compounds, pyrimidine derivatives as new wheat growth regulators will reduce the use of toxic chemical herbicides, pesticides, and fungicides that accumulate in soil, plants, and end up in human and animal food [33 - 36]. Considering all the important aspects mentioned above, the use of synthetic compounds, pyrimidine derivatives as wheat growth regulators will have a significant economic effect and contribute to the solution of ecological problems for the environment.

This work is aimed at the screening of new wheat growth regulators among synthetic compounds, furopyrimidine derivatives.

Materials and methods. The chemical structures of new synthetic compounds, furopyrimidine derivatives (compounds № 1 – 12), studied in the work, are given in Table 1.

The regulatory effect of new furopyrimidine derivatives on wheat growth was compared with the effect of known synthetic compounds, derivatives of sodium and potassium salts of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine (Methyur, Kamethur) and plant hormone

auxin IAA (*1H*-indol-3-yl)acetic acid), the chemical structures of which are also given in Table 1.

All chemical compounds studied in the work were synthesized at the Department for Chemistry of Bioactive Nitrogen-Containing Heterocyclic Compounds, V.P. Kukhar Institute of Bioorganic Chemistry and Petrochemistry of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine. Auxin IAA (*1H*-indol-3-yl)acetic acid) was manufactured by Sigma-Aldrich, USA.

Table 1.

Chemical structures of auxin IAA (*1H*-indol-3-yl)acetic acid), synthetic compounds, derivatives of sodium and potassium salts of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine (Methyur, Kamethur), and furopyrimidine derivatives (compounds № 1 – 12)

IAA		<i>1H</i> -indol-3-ylacetic acid MW=175,19
Methyur		Sodium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine MW=165,17
Kamethur		Potassium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine MW=181,28
1		3-(2-methoxyethyl)-6-methyl-4-oxofuro[2,3- <i>d</i>]pyrimidine-5-carboxylic acid, MW=252
2		ethyl 3-(2-methoxyethyl)-6-methyl-4-oxofuro[2,3- <i>d</i>]pyrimidine-5-carboxylate, MW=280
3		3-(furan-2-ylmethyl)-6-methyl-4-oxofuro[2,3- <i>d</i>]pyrimidine-5-carboxylic acid, MW=274
4		3-cyclohexyl-6-methyl-4-oxofuro[2,3- <i>d</i>]pyrimidine-5-carboxylic acid, MW=276

5		3-cyclohexyl-6-methyl- <i>N</i> -naphthalen-1-yl-4-oxofuro[2,3- <i>d</i>]pyrimidine-5-carboxamide, MW=401
6		<i>N</i> -(4-chlorophenyl)-3-cyclohexyl-6-methyl-4-oxofuro[2,3- <i>d</i>]pyrimidine-5-carboxamide, MW=386
7		methyl 4-[(3-benzyl-6-methyl-4-oxofuro[2,3- <i>d</i>]pyrimidine-5-carbonyl)amino]benzoate, MW=417
8		3-benzyl- <i>N</i> -(4-chlorophenyl)-6-methyl-4-oxofuro[2,3- <i>d</i>]pyrimidine-5-carboxamide, MW=394
9		3-benzyl- <i>N</i> -(4-ethylphenyl)-6-methyl-4-oxofuro[2,3- <i>d</i>]pyrimidine-5-carboxamide MW=387
10		3-benzyl- <i>N</i> -(3,4-dimethylphenyl)-6-methyl-4-oxofuro[2,3- <i>d</i>]pyrimidine-5-carboxamide, MW=387

11		3-benzyl-6-methyl-N-(4-methylphenyl)-4-oxofuro[2,3-d]pyrimidine-5-carboxamide, MW=373
12		3-benzyl-6-methyl-4-oxofuro[2,3-d]pyrimidine-5-carboxylic acid, MW=284

Wheat treatment and growing conditions. The aim of this work was to study the regulatory effect of synthetic compounds, furopyrimidine derivatives (compounds № 1 – 12) on the growth of winter wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) variety Tyra. Before processing, the seeds were sterilized with 1 % KMnO_4 solution for 15 min, then treated with 96 % ethanol solution for 1 min, after which they were washed three times with sterile distilled water. After this procedure, wheat seeds were placed in the plastic cuvettes (each containing 25 - 30 seeds) on the perlite moistened with distilled water (control sample), or water solutions of auxin IAA (1*H*-indol-3-yl)acetic acid), or synthetic compounds, derivatives of sodium and potassium salts of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine (Methyur, Kamethur), or furopyrimidine derivatives (compounds № 1 – 12), used in a concentration of 10^{-7}M (experimental samples). Then the wheat seeds were placed in a thermostat for germination in the dark at a temperature of 20 - 22 °C. After 48 hours, wheat seedlings were placed in a climate chamber, where they were grown at 16/8 h light/dark conditions, at a temperature of 20 - 22 °C, light intensity of 3000 lux, and air humidity 60 - 80 %. Morphometric parameters of wheat plants (average length of shoots (mm) and average length of roots (mm)) were measured after 4 weeks according to methodological recommendations [37]. The morphometric parameters determined on the experimental wheat plants were compared with similar parameters of control plants and expressed in (%).

Determination of the content of photosynthetic pigments in wheat plants. Biochemical parameters of wheat plants (content of photosynthetic pigments ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)) were also measured after 4 weeks according to methodological recommendations [38, 39]. To perform the extraction of photosynthetic pigments, we homogenized a sample (500 mg) of wheat leaves in the porcelain mortar in a cooled at the temperature 10 °C 96 % ethanol at the ratio of 1:10 (weight: volume) with addition of 0,1 - 0,2 g CaCO_3 (to neutralize the plant acids). The 1 ml of obtained homogenate was centrifuged at 8000 g in a refrigerated centrifuge K24D (MLW, Engelsdorf, Germany) during 5 min at the temperature 4 °C. The obtained precipitate was washed three times, with 1 ml 96 % ethanol and centrifuged at above mentioned conditions. After this procedure, the

optical density of chlorophyll a, chlorophyll b and carotenoid in the obtained extract was measured using spectrophotometer Specord M-40 (Carl Zeiss, Germany).

The content of chlorophyll a, chlorophyll b, and carotenoids in wheat leaves was calculated in accordance with formula:

$$\text{Cchl a} = 13.36 \times A_{664.2} - 5.19 \times A_{648.6},$$

$$\text{Cchl b} = 27.43 \times A_{648.6} - 8.12 A_{664.2},$$

$$\text{Cchl (a + b)} = 5.24 \times A_{664.2} + 22.24 \times A_{648.6},$$

$$\text{Ccar} = (1000 \times A_{470} - 2.13 \times \text{Cchl a} - 97.64 \times \text{Cchl b}) / 209,$$

Where,

Cchl – concentration of chlorophylls ($\mu\text{g/ml}$),
Cchl a – concentration of chlorophyll a ($\mu\text{g/ml}$), Cchl b – concentration of chlorophyll b ($\mu\text{g/ml}$), Ccar – concentration of carotenoids ($\mu\text{g/ml}$), A – absorbance value at a proper wavelength in nm.

The chlorophyll and carotenoids content per 1 g of fresh weight (FW) of extracted from wheat leaves was calculated by the following formula (separately for chlorophyll a, chlorophyll b and carotenoids):

$$A_1 = (C \times V) / (1000 \times a_1),$$

Where, A_1 – content of chlorophyll a, chlorophyll b, or carotenoids (mg/g FW),

C - concentration of pigments ($\mu\text{g/ml}$),

V - volume of extract (ml),

a_1 - sample of leaves (g).

Biochemical parameters determined in the experimental wheat plants, compared with similar parameters determined in control plants, were expressed in %.

Statistical data analysis. Each experiment was performed three times. Statistical processing of the experimental data was carried out using Student's t-test with a significance level of $P \leq 0.05$; mean values \pm standard deviation (\pm SD) [40].

Results and Discussion.

The effect of furopyrimidine derivatives on morphometric parameters of wheat plants. It is known that plant hormones auxins together with cytokinins play an important role in controlling the growth of plant roots and shoots during vegetation stage [41, 42]. Our works show the auxin-like and cytokinin-like regulatory effects of known synthetic compounds, derivatives of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimi-

dine (Methyur, Kamethur) on the growth and development of plant roots, shoots and plant productivity [22 - 32].

Our current study revealed that new furoypyrimidine derivatives exhibit a regulatory effect similar to

the effect of auxin IAA and known synthetic compounds, derivatives of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine (Methyur, Kamethur) on the growth and development of wheat roots and shoots in the vegetative stage (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. The regulatory effect of auxin IAA, synthetic compounds, derivatives of sodium and potassium salts of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine (Methyur, Kamethur), and furoypyrimidine derivatives (compounds № 2, 3, 6, 9, 10, 11) in a concentration of $10^{-7}M$ on the growth of shoots and roots of 4-week-old winter wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) variety Tyra compared to control plants.

Morphometric parameters of wheat plants (average length of roots (mm) and average length of shoots (mm)), treated with synthetic compounds, furoypyrimidine derivatives in a concentration of $10^{-7}M$, significantly increased as compared to control wheat plants treated with distilled water (Fig. 2 and Fig. 3).

Synthetic compounds, furoypyrimidine derivatives № 2 - 4, 6 - 12 showed the highest regulatory effect on the parameters of roots (mm) of 4-week-old winter wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) variety Tyra, and the least - compounds № 1 and 5 (Fig. 2).

The average length of roots (mm) increased: in wheat plants treated with compounds № 2 - 4, 6 - 12 - by 21,72 - 39,08 %, and in wheat plants treated with compounds № 1 and 5 - by 9,8 - 15,48 %, according to the control plants (Fig. 2).

Auxin IAA, Methyur and Kamethur also showed a high regulatory effect, the average length of roots (mm) increased: in wheat plants treated with auxin IAA - by 20,49 %, in wheat plants treated with Methyur - by 25,02 %, in wheat plants treated with Kamethur - by 39,3 %, according to the control plants (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. The regulatory effect of auxin IAA, synthetic compounds, derivatives of sodium and potassium salts of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine (Methyur, Kamethur), and furoypyrimidine derivatives (compounds № 1 - 12) in a concentration of $10^{-7}M$ on the average length of roots (mm) of 4-week-old winter wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) variety Tyra compared to control plants.

Synthetic compounds, furoypyrimidine derivatives № 3, 7 - 11 showed the highest regulatory effect on the parameters of shoots (mm) of 4-week-old winter wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) variety Tyra, and the least - compounds № 1 and 5 (Fig. 3).

The average length of shoots (mm) increased: in wheat plants treated with compounds № 3, 7 - 11 - by

7,37 - 24,51 %, and in wheat plants treated with compounds № 1 and 5 - by 4,21 - 5,15 %, according to the control plants (Fig. 3).

Auxin IAA, Methyur and Kamethur also showed a high regulatory effect, the average length of shoots (mm) increased: in wheat plants treated with auxin IAA - by 9,47 %, in wheat plants treated with Methyur - by

18,84 %, in wheat plants treated with Kamethur - by 11,69 %, according to the control plants (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. The regulatory effect of auxin IAA, synthetic compounds, derivatives of sodium and potassium salts of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine (Methyur, Kamethur), and furoypyrimidine derivatives (compounds № 1 - 12) in a concentration of $10^{-7}M$ on the average length of shoots (mm) of 4-week-old winter wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) variety Tyra compared to control plants.

At the same time, the average length of shoots (mm) in wheat plants treated with compounds № 2, 4, 6, and 12 did not statistically significantly differ from the control plants (Fig. 3).

Summarizing the obtained data, it should be noted that synthetic compounds, furoypyrimidine derivatives № 2 - 4, 6, 8 - 12 showed the highest regulatory effect on the average length of roots (mm) in wheat plants, and synthetic compounds, furoypyrimidine derivatives № 3, 7 - 11 showed the highest regulatory effect on the average length of shoots (mm) in wheat plants. Their regulatory effect was similar to the effect of auxin IAA, or synthetic compounds, derivatives of sodium and potassium salts of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine (Methyur, Kamethur), which are known as auxin-like and cytokinin-like compounds due to their regulatory effect on the growth of plant shoots and roots [22 - 32]. It is obvious that the high growth regulatory effect of synthetic compounds, furoypyrimidine derivatives № 2 - 4, 6 - 12 is due to their specific auxin-like regulatory effect on the proliferation, elongation and differentiation of plant cells, which are the basic processes of the formation and development of shoots and the roots in wheat plants [41, 42].

The effect of furoypyrimidine derivatives on biochemical parameters of wheat plants. As is known,

Concentration of chlorophylls and carotenoids, $\mu\text{g/ml}$

Figure 4. The regulatory effect of auxin IAA, synthetic compounds, derivatives of sodium and potassium salts of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine (Methyur, Kamethur), and furoypyrimidine derivatives (compounds № 1 - 12) in a concentration of $10^{-7}M$ on the content of chlorophylls a, b, a+b and carotenoids ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) in the leaves of 4-week-old winter wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) variety Tyra compared to control plants.

photosynthetic pigments chlorophylls and carotenoids play a key role in photosynthesis and photoprotection of plants and ensure their productivity [13 - 16, 38, 39]. Our previously published works showed that the known synthetic compounds, derivatives of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine (Methyur, Kamethur) exhibit auxin-like and cytokinin-like regulatory effects on the synthesis of photosynthetic pigments chlorophylls and carotenoids in plant leaves [23 - 26, 28, 29, 31]. This fact can be explained by the cytokinin-like regulatory effect of synthetic compounds Methyur and Kamethur on increasing the synthesis and slowing down the degradation of chlorophyll a, b and carotenoids in plant cells, which play a key role in photosynthesis and plant productivity [13 - 16].

As current research has shown, new furoypyrimidine derivatives exhibit a regulatory effect similar to the effect of auxin IAA and known synthetic compounds, derivatives of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine (Methyur, Kamethur) on the biochemical parameters (content of chlorophyll a, chlorophyll b, chlorophylls a+b, and carotenoids ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)) in the leaves of the 4-week-old winter wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) variety Tyra (Fig. 4).

The content of chlorophyll a ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) in the leaves of wheat plants exceeded the similar parameters of the control wheat plants: by 35,31 % - after treatment with auxin IAA, by 57,96 % - after treatment with Methyur, by 51,41 % - after treatment with Kamethur, by 16 – 47,8 % - after treatment with the most active synthetic compounds, furopyrimidine derivatives № 2, 3, 6–11, respectively (Fig. 4).

The content of chlorophyll b ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) in the leaves of wheat plants exceeded the similar parameters of the control wheat plants: by 27,33 % - after treatment with auxin IAA, by 51,2 % - after treatment with Methyur, by 53,33 % - after treatment with Kamethur, by 31,48 – 139 % - after treatment with the most active synthetic compounds, furopyrimidine derivatives № 2, 3, 6 – 11, respectively (Fig. 4).

The content of chlorophyll a+b ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) in the leaves of wheat plants exceeded the similar parameters of the control wheat plants: by 33,36 % - after treatment with auxin IAA, by 56,32 % - after treatment with Methyur, by 51,87 % - after treatment with Kamethur, by 30,46 – 65,12 % - after treatment with the most active synthetic compounds, furopyrimidine derivatives № 2, 3, 6 – 11, respectively (Fig. 4).

The content of carotenoids ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) in the leaves of wheat plants exceeded the similar parameters of the control wheat plants: by 31,22 % - after treatment with auxin IAA, by 50,81 % - after treatment with Methyur, by 45,58 % - after treatment with Kamethur, by 19,75 – 119 % - after treatment with the most active synthetic compounds, furopyrimidine derivatives № 2, 3, 6 – 11, respectively (Fig. 4).

The regulatory effect of synthetic compounds, furopyrimidine derivatives № 1, 4, 5, 12 was lower. The content of chlorophyll a, chlorophyll b, chlorophylls a+b, and carotenoids ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) in the leaves of wheat plants treated with synthetic compounds, furopyrimidine derivatives № 1, 4, 5, 12, exceeded the similar parameters of the control wheat plants: chlorophyll a increased by 21,33 – 27,7 %, chlorophyll b increased by 24,59 – 42,34 %, chlorophylls a+b increased by 4,30 – 27,15 %, carotenoids increased by 20,73 – 48,02 %, respectively (Fig. 4).

Analyzing the relationship between chemical structure and regulatory effect of synthetic compounds, furopyrimidine derivatives on the morphometric and biochemical parameters of wheat plants, it can be assumed that their regulatory effect on the growth and photosynthesis of wheat plants is related to the presence of substituents in their chemical structure (Table 1).

It is possible that the high regulatory effect of most active synthetic compounds, furopyrimidine derivatives № 2 – 4, 6 – 11 on the growth and photosynthesis of wheat plants, is associated with the presence of substituents in their chemical structure: compound № 2 contains a 2-methoxyethyl substituent in position 3, a methyl group in position 6, and a carboxylic acid ethyl ester group in position 5 of the 4-oxofuro[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine ring; compound № 3 contains a furan-2-ylmethyl substituent in position 3, a methyl group in position 6, and a carboxyl group in position 5 of the 4-oxofuro[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine ring; compound № 4 contains a cyclo-

hexyl substituent in position 3, a methyl group in position 6, and a carboxyl group in position 5 of the 4-oxofuro[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine ring; compound № 6 contains a cyclohexyl substituent in position 3, a methyl group in position 6, and a *N*-(4-chlorophenyl)amide substituent in position 5 of the 4-oxofuro[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine ring; compound № 7 contains a benzyl substituent in position 3, a methyl group in position 6, and a methyl 4-amidobenzoate substituent in position 5 of the 4-oxofuro[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine ring; compound № 8 contains a benzyl substituent in position 3, a methyl group in position 6, and a *N*-(4-chlorophenyl)amide substituent in position 5 of the 4-oxofuro[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine ring; compound № 9 contains a benzyl group in position 3, a methyl group in position 6, and a 4-ethylphenylamide group in position 5 of the 4-oxofuro[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine ring; compound № 10 contains a benzyl group in position 3, a methyl group in position 6, and a *N*-(3,4-dimethylphenyl)amide group in position 5 of the 4-oxofuro[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine ring; compound № 11 contains a benzyl group in position 3, a methyl group in position 6, and a 4-methylphenylamide group in position 5 of the 4-oxofuro[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine ring.

The decrease of the regulatory effect of synthetic compounds, furopyrimidine derivatives № 1, 5, 12 on the growth and photosynthesis of wheat plants can be explained by the presence of substituents in their chemical structures: compound № 1 contains a 2-methoxyethyl substituent in position 3, a methyl group in position 6, and a carboxyl group in position 5 of the 4-oxofuro[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine ring; compound № 5 contains a cyclohexyl substituent in position 3, a methyl group in position 6, and a *N*-(naphthalen-1-yl)amide substituent in position 5 of the 4-oxofuro[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine ring; compound № 12 contains a benzyl group in position 3, a methyl group in position 6, and a carboxyl group in position 5 of the 4-oxofuro[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine ring.

Based on theoretical and practical results of published works devoted to the study of phytohormones auxins and cytokinins or their synthetic analogues [43 - 59], it is assumed that the auxin-like and cytokinin-like regulatory effects of synthetic compounds, furopyrimidine derivatives on the growth and photosynthesis of wheat plants are realized due to their modulation of the activity of key enzymes of biosynthesis, transport, metabolism, conjugation, and oxidation of endogenous auxins and cytokinins in plant cells, as well as due to their modulation of auxin and cytokinin signaling pathways in plant cells.

Conclusion. The regulatory effect of furopyrimidine derivatives on the growth and photosynthesis of winter wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) variety Tyra in the vegetative stage was carried out. The conducted study showed that synthetic compounds, furopyrimidine derivatives exhibit selective regulatory effects on the growth of wheat roots and shoots, as well as on the biosynthesis of photosynthetic pigments in plant leaves. Compounds № 2 – 4, 6 – 12 significantly improve the growth of plant shoots and roots, and compounds № 2, 3, 6 – 11 significantly increase the content of photosynthetic pigments in the leaves of wheat plants. Synthetic

compounds, derivatives of furopyrimidine № 1, 5, 7 showed less regulatory effect on the growth of roots and shoots of wheat plants, and compounds № 1, 4, 5 and 12 showed less regulatory effect on the content of photosynthetic pigments in the leaves of wheat plants. Based on the obtained morphometric and biochemical parameters of wheat plants, it is possible to propose the practical use of synthetic compounds, derivatives of sodium and potassium salts of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine (Methyur, Kamethur), and most active furopyrimidine derivatives № 2 – 4, 6 – 11 in a concentration of 10^{-7} M for improving the growth of roots and shoots and increasing the content of photosynthetic pigments in winter wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) variety Tyra during the vegetative stage.

Statement of conflict of interest.

The authors are declared that they have no conflict with this research article.

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